

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF SOME SCHIFF BASES IN AQUEOUS MEDIUM AT 30°

Ligand	Cu(II)		Ni(II)		Zn(II)			Co(II)	
	log K ₁	log β ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log β ₂
Salicylidene-glycine	12.55	—	7.67	11.41	7.05	—	—	—	—
Salicylidene-α-alanine	11.44	—	6.49	9.97	6.50	11.58	15.60	—	—
Salicylidene-aspartic acid	14.00	—	8.42	—	7.32	10.46	—	8.50	11.53
Salicylidene-glutamic acid	10.46	—	8.78	11.35	7.28	11.30	—	7.40	10.82

TABLE 3—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF SOME SCHIFF BASES IN 50% ETHANOLIC MEDIUM AT 30°

Ligand	Cu(II)		Ni(II)		Zn(II)			Co(II)			Mn(II)	
	log K ₁	log β ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂	log K ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log β ₂	log β ₃	log K ₁	log β ₂
Salicylidene-glycine	14.38	18.27	10.58	15.59	9.76	14.91	18.36	9.38	13.57	—	6.68	10.01
5-Chloro-salicylidene-glycine	13.10	16.91	8.83	12.83	8.99	13.64	16.54	9.12	13.05	—	6.65	11.01
5-Bromo-salicylidene-glycine	13.60	—	10.71	16.96	9.68	15.24	18.59	9.71	15.50	18.2	5.87	9.27
5-Methyl-salicylidene-glycine	14.61	18.20	10.67	15.47	9.98	14.50	—	9.67	13.90	—	6.63	10.44

appears that the Zn(II) complexes have a different type of coordination and structure than the other complexes, which are known to form the octahedral complexes.

An examination of the log K₁ values of the metal complexes in Table 2 shows that the order of stabilities is Cu(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II) in most cases, and in the two cases studied the order is Co(II) > Ni(II) > Zn(II). This order is not much different from the Irving-Williams order of Mn(II) < Fe(II) < Co(II) < Ni(II) < Cu(II) > Zn(II).

The stabilities of the Schiff base complexes depend primarily on the strength of the C=N bond, the basicity of the imino group, the denticity of the Schiff base and steric factors¹⁰. The presence of the CH₃ substituent in α-alanine definitely lowers the stability constant by making the imine nitrogen less basic and hence a weaker donor of electrons to the metal ions. However, it is difficult to explain why the aspartic acid-Schiff base complexes are stronger than the glutamic acid-Schiff base complexes, which are both stronger than the glycine- or the α-alanine-Schiff base complexes, on the basis of the strength of the C=N bond and the basicities of the imine nitrogen only. A possible explanation in terms of the steric aspect of their structures has been given elsewhere¹¹.

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Electro Reduction of *Cis-Trans*-Isomers of Co(III) Complexes of the Type

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EXTENSIVE studies have been made previously on the geometric isomers of various metal ions¹⁻³, using different techniques. Recently, the polarographic technique has been successfully used for the purpose of identification of *cis-trans*-isomers of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{SO}_3)_2]^-$.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H., AnalaR grade. The solutions were prepared in double distilled water. An automatic pen recording CIC (Baroda, India) polarograph was used to record the polarograms. Purified nitrogen gas was used for removing the dissolved oxygen.

The pH of the test solution was adjusted with $\text{HNO}_3/\text{NH}_4\text{OH}$ solution. An Elico digital pH meter was used for pH measurements. All the observations were made at room temperature $24 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m^{2/3}t^{1/3} = 2.130 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{1/3}$. The *cis* and *trans* isomers of Co(III) complexes of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]^+$ were prepared² by taking $2 \times 10^{-3} M$ Co^{2+} ions, and their polarograms were recorded at different pH values. 1.0M Potassium chloride and 0.001% gelatin were used as supporting electrolyte and maximum suppressor, respectively. The ionic strength of the test solution was kept constant at $\mu = 1.0$ (KCl).

Results and Discussion

Each of the *cis* and *trans* isomers of $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4(\text{NO}_2)_2]^+$ gives a single reduction wave at and above pH 10.0 for *cis* isomer and at and above pH 11.0 for *trans* isomer, respectively. However, both the isomers give a single reduction wave at and below pH 4.0. A two stage reduction is observed for both the isomers if the pH is fixed between 4-10 in the former case and 4-11 in the latter case. The two stage reduction of cobalt complexes may be due to the conversion of Co(III) complex to Co(II) complex and Co(II) complex to cobalt metal³⁻⁵. This has been confirmed by calculating the value of number of electrons 'n' involved in each electro-reduction process by millicoulometric method⁷. In all the cases the reduction of both the *cis* and *trans* isomers under study was found to be diffusion controlled as indicated by the linearity of i_a vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$ plots and their passing through the origin.

Though both the isomers have a small decrease in their $E_{1/2}$ values at different pH values, these are separated by a little over 0.10 V at pH 4.0. This pH may, therefore, be recommended as a suitable pH for the identification of the two isomers. Further, the *cis*-isomer is reduced at a more positive potential than the *trans* form. The observed shift in the half wave potentials of the two forms is based on an argument that the preferred orientation of the *cis* complex is due to the large internal dipole at a positive surface⁸.

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Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Mn(II) by Some Uni- and Polyvalent Anions vis-a-vis the Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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IN continuation of our earlier publication¹ on the suppression of polarographic negative maximum of Mn(II) by some uni- and polyvalent cations, we report here the results of our investigation on the suppression of this maximum by some uni- and polyvalent anions viz., Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , NO_3^- , CNS^- , SO_4^{2-} , $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$, PO_4^{3-} and $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ vis-a-vis the kinetics of the electrode reaction.

Experimental

All the experimental details were the same as reported earlier¹.

Results and Discussion

The experimental conditions such as the concentration of the depolarizer, the concentration of the supporting electrolyte (KCl), pH and the height of mercury column were adjusted in a way as to get a sharp and well-defined maximum of Mn(II) and these conditions were kept the same in all the cases. The concentration of the depolarizer was kept at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ and that of the supporting electrolyte at 0.05 M, the pH of the medium was adjusted to 6.0 and the height of the mercury column (h_{corr}) was 71.45 cm.

The first kind polarographic maximum of Mn(II) under the chosen experimental conditions appears at -1.53 V (vs SCE) and lies well on the negative side of the potential of the electrocapillary zero under the same experimental conditions. Since the $E_{1/2}$ of Mn(II) also lies on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero, the maximum of Mn(II) is of negative polarity^{2a}.

A perusal of Table 1 shows that E_{max} gets shifted to positive potentials with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent anions. This positive shift in E_{max} can be explained as below.

Polarographic maximum of the first kind is caused by streaming of the solution from the bulk to the drop, thereby bringing the depolarizer to the electrode surface in excess of the quantity supposed to be brought by diffusion alone. Therefore, the current rises above the limiting diffusion current. This streaming is caused by motion in the inner

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